

Internship Report

**Translating Booklet and Website Contents to Increase Boyolali Tourism
Promotion at Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency**

**Submitted to Meet a Part of the Requirements to Obtain
Ahli Madya Degree in English Language**

By:

Latifah Puji Hastuti

B3117020

English Diploma Program

Vocational School

Universitas Sebelas Maret

Surakarta

2020

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Firstly, I would like to say Alhamdulillah to Allah SWT for blessing and guiding me during my internship program. I would like to express deep appreciation to myself who did it from the beginning until the end. I would like to thank you to my dearest parents, sisters and brothers who have supported me in this field.

Secondly, I would like to express a big grateful to Ardianna Nuraeni, S.S., M.Hum as the head of English Diploma Program. She has already advised me throughout the internship program. I would express my deep appreciation to Dr. Ida Kusuma Dewi, M.A. as my supervisor. She has already given instruction, guidance, and motivation to me. I would like to thank you her carefulness in guiding me wrote the report. I also say thank you to Drs. Agus Hari Wibowo, Ph.D., Nur Saptaningsih, S.Hum., M.Hum and other lectures of English Diploma Program.

Thirdly, I say thank you to Mr. Susilo the Head Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency who has already given me permission to do internship program. Thank you for all of opportunities. I would like to say thank you to Mrs. Naniek Irawati, S.sen as the Head Department of Marketing, Mr. Djoko Irjati, S.T as the Head Section of Promotion and my Supervisor in the office. I also say thank you to other staffs who have already given me opportunity, experience and knowledge.

Last but not least, I would like to thank you to my close friends, all of my colleagues, my seniors who have already given the support and contribution for me from all aspects.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

APPROVAL.....	ii
ACCEPTANCE	iii
ACKNOWLEDGMENT	iv
TABLE OF CONTENT	v
LIST OF TABLES	vii
LIST OF FIGURES	viii
ABSTRACT	ix
Chapter 1 Introduction	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Place and Time of Internship	2
1.3 Benefits of Internship	3
1.3.1 Benefits for Student	3
1.3.2 Benefits for Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency	3
1.3.3 Benefits for English Diploma Program	4
Chapter 2 Department of Youth, Sport, and Tourism of Boyolali Regency.....	5
2.1 Profile Department of Youth, Sport, and Tourism of Boyolali Regency.....	5
2.2 Visions and Missions of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism	5
2.3 The Organizational Structure of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism	6
2.4 Job and duties	8
2.4.1 The Head Office Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency	8
2.4.2 Secretariat	8
2.4.3 Youth Division	8
2.4.4 Sports Division	9
2.4.5 Destination and Tourism Industry Division	9
2.4.6 Marketing and Institutional Tourism Division	9

2.5 Media Publication at Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism	10
Chapter 3 Internship Activities	11
3.1 General Activities	11
3.2 Main Activity	12
3.2.1 Translating Booklet of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency	12
3.2.2 Translating Website of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency	23
3.3 The tools that used during Internship Program	25
3.4 Additional Activity	26
3.5 Problems and Solutions during translating Booklet of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency	27
3.6 Problems and Solutions during translating Website of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency	29
Chapter 4 Conclusion and Recommendation	33
4.1 Conclusion.....	33
4.2 Recommendation	34
REFERENCES	37
APPENDICES	38

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.2.1 The example of transferring	13
Table 3.2.2 The example of transferring	15
Table 3.2.3 The example of transferring	16
Table 3.2.4 The example of restructuring	18
Table 3.2.5 The example of restructuring	20
Table 3.2.6 The example of transferring	23
Table 3.2.7 The example of restructuring	24
Table 10 Translation result of Website Contents.....	48
Table 11 Translation result of copywriting result.....	60

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 2.3 Organizational Structure of Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency.....	7
Figure 3.2.1 Reference of translation	14
Figure 3.2.2 Reference of translation	15
Figure 3.2.3 Reference of translation	16
Figure 3.2.4 Reference of translation	16
Figure 3.2.5 Reference of translation	19
Figure 3.2.6 Reference of translation	19
Figure 3.2.7 Reference of translation	20
Figure 3.2.8 Reference of translation	21
Figure 3.2.9 Reference of translation	22
Figure 3.2.10 Reference of translation	22
Figure 3.2.11 Reference of translation	24
Figure 13 The example of Booklet	39
Figure 14 The example of Booklet	40
Figure 15 The example of Booklet	41
Figure 16 The example of Booklet	42
Figure 17 The example of Booklet	43
Figure 18 The example of Booklet	44
Figure 19 The example of Booklet	45
Figure 20 The example of Booklet	46
Figure 21 The example of Booklet	47
Figure 22 The Documentation of Internship Program	64

ABSTRACT

Latifah Puji Hastuti, 2020. Translating Booklet and Website Contents to Increase Boyolali Tourism Promotion at Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency. English Diploma Program, Vocational School, Universitas Sebelas Maret.

This report is written based on internship program at Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency started from January 8, 2020 to March 8, 2020. The main objective of the internship is to increase the tourism promotion at Department of Youth, Sports and Tourism of Boyolali Regency. There were two main projects that I did during the internship program. They include translating booklet and website contents. There was additional activity for supporting my skill. It was copywriting content. Three steps that I did to finish my translation projects were Analyzing, Transferring, and Restructuring. I encountered some problems in translating projects. Those problems include incomplete sentences, difficulty to find equivalent words, unnatural sentences in the source text, ambiguous sentences, some words do not have any direct equivalences in the target language due to Javanese cultural terms and words related to concepts which are not lexicalized in the target language, and ineffective sentences. There were many solutions to overcome those problems. One of them was reading over and over the text.